

A D-Band Scalable and LO-Less Time-Modulated Multi-Beam Active Relay Array with Broadcasting Capability for 6G Distributed MIMO Networks

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Abstract—This paper presents a scalable D-band active reflective relay array that can enable non-line-of-sight (NLOS) wireless communication links with multi-beam reception and broadcasting capabilities, targeting 6G Distributed MIMO (D-MIMO) applications. By adopting two time-modulated linear periodically time-varying (LPTV) arrays at the receiving and transmitting frontends of the relay, the proposed relay concurrently receives/transmits multiple beams with multiple independent data streams from and to multiple spatially distinct wireless nodes. The local oscillator (LO)-less scheme of the proposed relay further obviates the losses and power consumption of mixers and LO distribution, ensuring a low-cost, low-complexity, and scalable relay array design. As a proof of concept, a D-band 120-GHz relay array prototype with 8-element transmitter (TX) array and 8-element receiver (RX) array is implemented in GlobalFoundries (GF) 22nm CMOS FD-SOI technology. The prototype relay implementation is fully integrated with on-chip orthogonally-polarized RX/TX antenna arrays. By post-processing the fabricated chips, substrate grooves are created at the back side of the chips to partially suppress the substrate modes and enhance the isolation between the RX and TX antenna arrays. Over-the-air (OTA) measurement results demonstrate successful 120-GHz 16-QAM 1 and 2 Gbps per beam NLOS wireless links through the relay with an EVM_{RMS} of 6.4% and 8.9% respectively in the case of one external transmitting node communicating through the relay with up to six receiving nodes. The measurements also demonstrate an EVM_{RMS} of 9.5% and 12.2% respectively in the case of two external transmitting nodes communicating through the relay with up to five receiving nodes.

Index Terms—Beamforming, D-band, Distributed MIMO (D-MIMO), linear periodically time-varying (LPTV) system, multi-beam, non-line-of-sight (NLOS) communication, phased-array, reflective surface, scalable relay, time-modulation.

I. INTRODUCTION

DUE to the growing demand for higher data-rates and channel throughputs, the mm-Wave and sub-THz spectrums have been actively explored for beyond-5G and 6G

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wireless communication and sensing [1]–[3]. While large-scale phased arrays with pencil-sharp beams prove to be useful in overcoming the severe free-space path loss in line-of-sight (LOS) channels at mm-Wave [4]–[11] and sub-THz [12]–[17], reconfigurable relays and reflective surfaces are envisioned to enhance the reliability of future communication networks by creating NLOS wireless links between the original TX and the target RX, enabling NLOS communication [18]–[20].

A growing number of CMOS passive and active relays have been recently reported at mm-Wave and sub-THz frequencies [21]–[25]. In [21], a single-beam 25-GHz decentralized active relay array based on true time delay is reported. A single-beam 265-GHz 98×98 -unit passive reflect-array with beam squint correction capability is presented in [22]. In [23], a tunable single-beam active relay with phase-shifter based beamforming is reported across 57-64 GHz. In [24], a scalable multi-beam active relay array is reported at 28 GHz based on true time delay and N -path filtering. In [25], a scalable single-beam reconfigurable active relay array with 2-D angle-of-arrival detection capability is reported at 120 GHz.

On the other hand, dynamic arrays that utilize joint space-time-frequency modulation techniques besides standard phase-amplitude modulation are getting rapidly increasing research interest [26]–[34]. In [26], time-modulation is applied to a 28-GHz phased array IC to perform spatio-temporal filtering and precise beam control. In [27], [28], space-time modulation is utilized to implement a 71-76 GHz mm-Wave transmitter array with physical layer security. In [29], a time-modulated multi-beam multi-user MIMO receiver array using a single beamformer and a single wire interface is reported at 28 GHz. [30] proposes a 5-GHz 5×5 metasurface with 2-D direction-of-arrival estimation capability, achieved by time modulating partial of the metasurface elements. In [31], a 4-element dynamic time-modulated TX array is cascaded with a 4-element static Butler matrix to produce 20 concurrent beams at 125 GHz. In [32], frequency-modulation is proposed to implement a 28-GHz 4-element mm-Wave transmitter array with super angular resolution for joint communication and sensing. In [33], a reconfigurable phase-time mm-Wave TX array at 28 GHz is proposed for physical layer security and multi-target localization. In [34], a 28-GHz TX array with a dynamic subset antenna modulation is proposed for low-overhead physical layer security.

Most reported relays can only establish a single communication link between one external pair of TX/RX nodes [21]–

[23], [25], [30]. Although the decentralized active relay array reported in [24] offers multi-beam capability, it experiences high-complexity array scalability over frequency and/or array size as the received data is processed inside the relay at an intermediate frequency (IF), requiring a pair of down/up-conversion mixers and a LO signal for every element. In addition, the IF data processing is power hungry, which increases its relay element power consumption to 472 mW for a saturated output power of 3 dBm.

Desired relay array solutions should support concurrent multi-beams/multi-streams, low complexity, and array scalability simultaneously. To address these challenges, this work proposes a D-band scalable and LO-less active relay array with multi-beam capabilities at both the RX and the TX sides, achieving: (1) simultaneously receiving multiple beams with independent data streams from different external wireless TX nodes, and (2) directly broadcasting these streams out to multiple external wireless RX nodes in different directions. The proposed relay architecture uses time-modulation at both of its RX and TX array frontends, and the resulting LPTV dynamic operation on the RX/TX arrays realizes the concurrent multi-streams and multi-beams in both reception and transmission. Unlike conventional multi-beam MIMO arrays, which either use a sub-array for each beam or one separate set of phase shifters and beamformer for each beam, the proposed time-modulated relay array utilizes the full array aperture for each beam without any additional phase shifters or beamformers. The LO-less scheme of the proposed relay also avoids mixers and LO distribution to obviate their losses and power for low relay complexity and array scalability. In addition, the time-modulation clock signals are only required to operate at the modulation rate (up to 1 GHz in this work) that is much lower than the carrier frequency (120 GHz in this work). Therefore, the generation and distribution of these time-modulation clock signals exhibit less power and complexity than generating and buffering the LO signals, justifying the low-power and low-complexity nature of the proposed LO-less time-modulated multi-beam active relay array. Further, the beams/streams are processed only in the radio frequency (RF) domain, enabling low-latency communication.

The applications of the proposed multi-beam relay architecture with broadcasting capability include the envisioned 6G D-MIMO networks for fronthaul mobile communication [35]–[38] and advanced factory automation [39]–[41]. In the 6G D-MIMO fronthaul communications, multiple fixed-location Distributed Units (DUs) need to communicate with multiple fixed-location Radio Units (RUs), and low-latency two-way communication is the key to ensure high data rate and RUs' timing synchronization, so that the network of RUs can form coherent distributed MIMOs with mobile User Equipments (UEs). In the 6G D-MIMO factory automation applications, similar networks will be formed with multiple fixed-location DUs and fixed-location robots, where low latency and timing synchronization is even more critical for advanced manufacturing. In both 6G D-MIMO applications, the multi-beam reception and broadcasting capabilities of the proposed relay can directly enhance the latency, reliability, and throughput of these networks. Fig. 1(a) provides a detailed illustration

Fig. 1. Applications of the proposed multi-beam relay with broadcasting capability (a) D-MIMO networks for fronthaul mobile communications involving fixed DUs and RUs (b) D-MIMO networks for advanced factory automation.

of the fronthauls for the D-MIMO network proposed in [35], where fixed DUs need to simultaneously communicate with multiple fixed RUs that further connect with mobile UEs in mobile wireless applications. In such scenario, the proposed relay architecture can prove extremely beneficial by simultaneously receiving the multiple data streams from the DUs and broadcasting them, on the fly, to the RUs with low latency and high throughput. Moreover, the broadcasting ability enables the DUs and RUs to potentially access the full information from all the streams, radically enhancing the D-MIMO's capability of managing the massive data flow with robustness and flexibility and minimizing switching information among beams for ultra-low latency. In parallel, the details of utilizing 6G D-MIMO networks in advanced factory automation schemes are presented in Fig. 1(b). In such schemes, active relays based on the proposed architecture can be installed to simultaneously collect the data from multiple DUs and then broadcast the collected data to multiple sensor nodes distributed across the manufacturing factory.

Fig. 2. Time-modulation LPTV multi-user MIMO RX array architecture, where the down-conversion mixer and LO are included only to facilitate the IF spectrum analysis and are not required by the operation of the time-modulated RX array.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section II, time-modulated RX and TX arrays are briefly analyzed to show how their LPTV nature can respectively realize concurrent multi-beam space-to-spectrum and spectrum-to-space mapping. The proposed time-modulated multi-beam relay architecture with broadcasting capability is then presented in Section III, along with a test scenario based on theoretical behavior modeling to demonstrate its RX/TX multi-beam capabilities. Section IV analyzes the top-level aspects and design considerations of the proposed system. The implementation details of a 120-GHz 1×8 RX/TX relay array prototype in GF 22nm CMOS FD-SOI technology are discussed in Section V. In Section VI, the OTA measurement results of the relay prototype are presented, and the relay capabilities and performance are compared to reported state-of-the-art mm-Wave and sub-THz relays. Finally, Section VII concludes the paper.

II. TIME-MODULATED ARRAYS

In this Section, the time-modulation operation on an RX array and a TX array are presented to show its LPTV beam-forming properties.

A. Time-Modulated RX Array

Consider an N -element RX array whose elements are periodically ON/OFF modulated as shown in Fig. 2. The time-modulation clocks are assumed to be non-overlapping and have equal width for simplicity, though overlapping/non-equal-width time-modulation is also feasible in practice, and can be used for sidebands and harmonics control [42]–[46]. By assuming the gain of the frontend is unity and the RX receives a plane wave whose phase propagation constant is k ($k = 2\pi/\lambda$ where λ is the wavelength) and has an everlasting sinusoidal dependence with frequency f_{RF} ($e^{j2\pi f_{RF}t}$), the overall array output ($A(\theta, t)$) of the time-modulated RX array can be expressed as [47]:

$$A(\theta, t) = \sum_{m=1}^N W_m(t) e^{jk(m-1)d \sin \theta} e^{j2\pi f_{RF}t} \quad (1)$$

where d is the spacing between the array elements, θ is the angle measured from the broadside direction of the antenna array, and $W_m(t)$ is the time-modulation waveform of the m^{th} element. $W_m(t)$ in the non-overlapping and equal-width case can be expressed as:

$$W_m(t) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \frac{(m-1)T_{TM}}{N} \leq t \leq \frac{mT_{TM}}{N} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where T_{TM} is the time-modulation period. Given the periodicity of $W_m(t)$, it can be expanded using Fourier series as:

$$W_m(t) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} a_n e^{j2\pi n f_{TM} t} \quad (3)$$

where f_{TM} is the time-modulation frequency ($f_{TM} = 1/T_{TM}$) and a_n are the Fourier series coefficients which can be calculated as:

$$a_n = \frac{1}{T_{TM}} \int_{T_{TM}} W_m(t) e^{-j2\pi n f_{TM} t} dt \quad (4)$$

$$= e^{-j\pi \frac{n}{N}(2m-1)} \frac{\sin(\pi n/N)}{\pi n}.$$

By substituting (4) into (3) and then substituting for $W_m(t)$ into (1), while assuming the antennas are spaced by $\lambda/2$ ($d = \lambda/2$), $A(\theta, t)$ can be finally written as:

$$A(\theta, t) = e^{j\psi} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} H_n e^{j2\pi(f_{RF} + n f_{TM})t} \quad (5)$$

where ψ and H_n are given by:

$$\psi = \frac{\pi}{2}(N-1) \sin \theta \quad (6)$$

$$H_n = (-1)^n \frac{\sin(\pi n/N)}{\pi n} \frac{\sin(\frac{N\pi}{2}(\sin \theta - \frac{2n}{N}))}{\sin(\frac{\pi}{2}(\sin \theta - \frac{2n}{N}))}. \quad (7)$$

Consequently, by dividing $A(\theta, t)$ by the input excitation ($e^{j2\pi f_{RF}t}$), the array factor ($AF(\theta, t)$) can be obtained as:

$$AF(\theta, t) = e^{j\psi} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} H_n e^{j2\pi n f_{TM} t}. \quad (8)$$

Fig. 3. Extending the time-modulation LPTV concept to a multi-beam TX array with broadcasting capability, where the up-conversion mixer and LO are included only to facilitate the IF spectrum analysis and are not required by the operation of the time-modulated TX array.

With the aid of the derived array factor expression in (8) for a time-modulated RX, we make the following observations. First, given that LPTV systems are characterized with their time-varying periodic response [48], the time-varying nature of the array factor in (8) reveals the LPTV characteristics of time-modulated arrays. This is distinct to conventional phased arrays whose array factor has no time-varying dependence. Second, as illustrated in Fig. 2, the array factor expression in (7) and (8) suggests that $(N+1)$ incident signals from different angles in space $\theta = \sin^{-1}(2n/N)$ at the same center frequency f_{RF} can be concurrently received, mapped, and frequency-multiplexed to different frequency components $f_{RF} \pm n f_{TM}$, where $n = 0, \pm 1, \dots, \pm N/2$. This demonstrates the capability of a time-modulated RX to operate as a multi-user MIMO RX with spatial multiplexing [29]. However, it is worth noting that f_{TM} should be chosen sufficiently larger than the modulation bandwidth to ensure Nyquist sampling without inter-beam aliasing. In addition, the LO and mixer shown in Fig. 2 just down-convert the spectrum to $f_{IF} \pm n f_{TM}$ and are not intrinsically necessary for the time-modulated LPTV RX operation; therefore both aspects are different from the N -path RX concept [49].

B. Time-Modulated TX Array

By reciprocity, a time-modulated TX array that is modulated with the time-modulation clocks given in (2) and is excited by a sinusoidal signal with frequency f_{RF} ($e^{j2\pi f_{RF}t}$) will have the same array output expressions derived in (5)-(8). The interpretation of this scenario is that the time-modulated TX array will simultaneously broadcast the same f_{RF} data stream to $(N+1)$ different space angles at different carrier frequency components, performing the reciprocal spectrum-to-space mapping. That is, by applying time-modulation on a multi-band/multi-stream TX input spectrum, as shown in Fig. 3, all the multi-streams will be simultaneously broadcast to different transmitting angles $\theta = \sin^{-1}(2n/N)$ with preserved signal fidelity. In addition, at each angle, the whole

data streams will be mapped to different frequencies offset by multiples of f_{TM} . Consequently, the end RX users can employ proper RX/LO frequencies and IF filter-banks to only pick-up their intended data streams (as their designated channels). Or, for the broadcasting scenario, they can choose to receive more or all the data streams. Again, the LO and mixer in Fig. 3 only perform up-conversion and are not necessary for the operation of the time-modulated LPTV TX array.

III. PROPOSED MULTI-BEAM RELAY ARCHITECTURE

The system architecture of the proposed relay is shown in Fig. 4, which combines a time-modulated N -element RX array and a time-modulated N -element TX array. The down/up-conversion mixers and LOs in the time-modulated RX and TX arrays shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 respectively are completely removed in the relay architecture to achieve a LO-less design with low signal losses, power, and complexity. Consequently, the output of the time-modulated RX array directly feeds the input of the time-modulated TX array at the junction node R . The relay RX array simultaneously receives different incoming beams with different data streams (modulations) and multiplexes them to different frequency components. Then, the relay TX array broadcasts these data streams to different spatial angles in space at different carrier frequency components. Finally, the end RX users at each spatial angle can pick the desired data stream/channel, from one to all the streams. Orthogonally polarized antennas are used at the RX and TX sides of the relay to suppress the direct coupling between the relay TX and RX arrays. It is worth noting that the time-modulation clock signals are only required to operate at the modulation rate (up to 1 GHz in this work) that is much lower than the carrier frequency (120 GHz in this work). Therefore, the generation and distribution of these time-modulation clock signals exhibit less power and complexity than generating and buffering the LO signals, justifying the low-power and low-complexity nature of the proposed LO-less time-modulated multi-beam active relay array.

Fig. 4. Proposed scalable and LO-less time-modulated LPTV multi-beam active relay array with broadcasting capability.

Fig. 5. Behavioral modeling of an 8-element time-modulated LPTV multi-beam relay based on the proposed architecture (a) test scenario setup where two 120-GHz CW signals are received by the relay from 0° and -30° (b) spectrum at the relay receiving side output (node R) demonstrating the space-to-spectrum mapping property (c) radiation patterns observed by the external receiver demonstrating the spectrum-to-space mapping and broadcasting capabilities achieved by the relay transmitting side.

The behavior modeling of an 8-element relay array is shown in Fig. 5 to verify its functionality. The setup of the applied test scenario is shown in Fig. 5(a) where two 120 GHz continuous-wave (CW) signals are concurrently received from 0° (D_1) and -30° (D_2) as two independent streams. As shown in Fig. 5(b), with $f_{TM} = 1$ GHz, D_1 and D_2 are mapped at the RX array output (node R in Fig. 4) to 120 GHz and 118 GHz respectively, demonstrating the space-to-spectrum mapping property of the relay RX array. The time-modulated LPTV TX array then, as shown in Fig. 5(c), with its spectrum-to-space mapping capability broadcasts these two streams to various angles in space at different frequency components. End RX users can receive either or both of these two streams (D_1 and D_2), showing the robustness and diversity of the established NLOS links. It is worth noting that compact D-

band phase shifters [50]–[52] can be further incorporated to steer the broadcasted TX beams of the relay altogether.

IV. SYSTEM CONSIDERATIONS

In this Section, the top-level aspects and design considerations of the proposed time-modulated multi-beam relay are analyzed.

A. Time-Modulation Switching Harmonics

For an N -element time-modulated RX array, due to the switching associated with the time-modulation operation, harmonics are generated at the output of each time-modulation switch as illustrated in Fig. 6(a). Nevertheless, due to the progressive phase shift in the received signal among the array

Fig. 6. Effect of time-modulation switching harmonics for (a) time-modulated RX arrays (b) time-modulated TX arrays.

elements and the non-overlapping time-modulation operation, when the N paths of the time-modulation array are combined (at node R), all the harmonics cancel out for a specific set of spatial angles except for one tone that uniquely identifies the reception angle. More specifically, as demonstrated by the derived time-modulation array factor that is given by (7) and by the behavior modeling example in Fig. 5, the $(N+1)$ spatial angles $\theta = \sin^{-1}(2n/N)$ (where $n = 0, \pm 1, \dots, \pm N/2$) get uniquely mapped (at node R) to $f_{RF} \pm n f_{TM}$, ideally without any impact among the $(N+1)$ received beams. Consequently, for the target 6G distributed-MIMO applications (in Fig. 1) of the proposed multi-beam relay, as long as the fixed DUs are located at some of the spatial angles $\theta = \sin^{-1}(2n/N)$, no undesirable harmonics will be ideally generated at the combining node R inside the relay.

In a similar manner, for an N -element time-modulated TX array as shown in Fig. 6(b), harmonics get generated at the outputs of the time-modulation switches. However, with spatial power combining, only one tone for each beam gets transmitted to each of the $(N+1)$ spatial angles $\theta = \sin^{-1}(2n/N)$ with the other harmonics being eliminated. Therefore, again, for the target 6G distributed-MIMO applications (in Fig. 1), as long as the RUs or sensors are placed at some of the spatial angles $\theta = \sin^{-1}(2n/N)$, the different transmitted beams by the time-modulated array of the relay's TX side will not impact each other.

Fig. 7. Spectrum at the combiner's node (node R) where $(N+1)$ independent beams can be multiplexed in frequency based on the time-modulation operation.

B. Time-Modulation Frequency Selection Criteria

As shown in Fig. 7, the time-modulation switching frequency (f_{TM}) should be judiciously selected to satisfy the Nyquist criteria and avoid inter-beam aliasing at the combining node (node R in Fig. 4). More rigorously, assuming the channel's bandwidth for each beam is B_{ch} and the minimum spacing needed between channels (to satisfy the IF filter requirements at final-end users) is B_{tr} , the minimum f_{TM} ($f_{TM,min}$) needed to avoid inter-beam aliasing is given by:

$$f_{TM,min} = B_{ch} + B_{tr}. \quad (9)$$

Accordingly, given a total operating RF bandwidth of B_{tot} , the maximum channel's bandwidth ($B_{ch,max}$), for each of the $(N+1)$ concurrent beams, can be expressed as:

$$B_{ch,max} = \frac{B_{tot} - NB_{tr}}{N+1}. \quad (10)$$

Typically, the spacing bandwidth is much smaller than the total operating RF bandwidth (i.e., $NB_{tr} \ll B_{tot}$). Therefore, $B_{ch,max}$ can be approximated by $B_{tot}/(N+1)$, meaning that the action of the proposed time-modulated relay is to distribute the total operating bandwidth B_{tot} equally among different $(N+1)$ frequency-multiplexed beams. It is worth noting that in cases when the beams have different occupied bandwidths, $f_{TM,min}$ should be chosen based on the beam with the largest bandwidth.

C. RX Analysis

The noise behavior of an N -element time-modulated RX frontend can be analyzed with the aid of Fig. 8. The analysis is carried out under the following assumptions: (a) the noise contribution of the time-modulation switch is negligible (a reasonable assumption with a sufficiently large LNA gain), (b) the noise random process is stationary (i.e., its statistics do not change over time), and (c) the noise sources of the N channels ($n_1(t)$, $n_2(t)$, ..., and $n_N(t)$) are sample functions of the same white random process $n(t)$ whose double-sided power spectral density is equal to P_n . We first derive the noise power spectral density at the elements' outputs (nodes E_1 , E_2 , ..., and E_N), and accordingly derive the noise power spectral density at node R (after the combiner).

The noise at node E_1 can be expressed in time-domain as:

$$E_1(t) = n_1(t)W_1(t). \quad (11)$$

 Fig. 8. Noise analysis of the N -element time-modulated RX frontend.

Since the noise $n_1(t)$ is a stochastic process and the time-modulation windowing function $W_1(t)$ is a deterministic signal, $E_1(t)$ is generally stochastic. Therefore, the power spectral density of $E_1(t)$ can be derived by calculating its autocorrelation function ($R_{E_1}(t, t + \tau)$), and then calculating the Fourier transform of $R_{E_1}(t, t + \tau)$. The autocorrelation function $R_{E_1}(t, t + \tau)$ can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} R_{E_1}(t, t + \tau) &= E[E_1(t)E_1(t + \tau)] \\ &= E[n_1(t)n_1(t + \tau)W_1(t)W_1(t + \tau)]. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Since $W_1(t)$ is deterministic, it can be taken outside the expectation operator, and accordingly $R_{E_1}(t, t + \tau)$ can be simplified to:

$$R_{E_1}(t, t + \tau) = W_1(t)W_1(t + \tau)R_{n_1}(t, t + \tau). \quad (13)$$

Under the assumption that $n_1(t)$ is stationary, its autocorrelation function $R_{n_1}(t, t + \tau)$ is independent of t and is only function in the time difference τ . Moreover, since $n_1(t)$ is assumed to be white, its autocorrelation function is equal to a Dirac delta function that is weighted by its power spectral density (P_n). Consequently, $R_{E_1}(t, t + \tau)$ can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} R_{E_1}(t, t + \tau) &= W_1(t)W_1(t + \tau)P_n\delta(\tau) \\ &= W_1^2(t)P_n\delta(\tau). \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

The power spectral density of $E_1(t)$ ($S_{E_1}(f)$) can now be derived by calculating the Fourier transform of $R_{E_1}(t, t + \tau)$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{E_1}(f) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} W_1^2(t)P_n\delta(\tau)e^{-j2\pi f\tau} d\tau \\ &= W_1^2(t)P_n \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

which is periodic with a period of T_{TM} , and can be expressed over one period of T_{TM} as:

$$S_{E_1}(f) = \begin{cases} P_n, & \text{if } 0 \leq t \leq \frac{T_{TM}}{N} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

Since the power spectral density $S_{E_1}(f)$ varies periodically over time with a period of T_{TM} , the random process at node E_1 is considered to be cyclostationary with a power spectral density toggling between P_n ($1/N$ of the time) and 0

($(N-1)/N$ of the time). In a similar manner, the same analysis can be repeated for the other elements' outputs (E_2, E_3, \dots , and E_N) showing that they exhibit cyclostationary random processes that have a period of T_{TM} and with the power spectral density of the m^{th} element (at node E_m) given by:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{E_m}(f) &= W_m^2(t)P_n \\ &= \begin{cases} P_n, & \text{if } \frac{(m-1)T_{TM}}{N} \leq t \leq \frac{mT_{TM}}{N} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Now, by summing for the N elements, the noise autocorrelation function at the summing node (node R) can be calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned} R_R(t, t + \tau) &= (W_1^2(t) + W_2^2(t) + \dots + W_N^2(t))P_n\delta(\tau) \\ &= P_n\delta(\tau) \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

which is stationary and has double-sided power spectral density of P_n . Interestingly, it can be concluded that although the noise random processes at nodes E_1, E_2, \dots , and E_N are cyclostationary, the noise random process after the combiner (node R) turns out to be stationary and exhibit the same power spectral density as the noise of any of the N elements (before the time-modulation switch). This can be intuitively interpreted in the time-domain, as shown in Fig. 8, by noting that the combining node R is only affected by one element noise contribution at any time instant due to the non-overlapping time-modulation scheme.

In order to clarify the design trade-offs between time-modulated RX arrays versus single-beam and multi-beam analog/digital RX beamformers, a performance comparison is presented in Fig. 9. The main performance metrics, being considered, are the number of concurrent beams, the overall throughput of each architecture, the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) per beam after beamforming, and the implementation complexity of each architecture if implemented in a relay. As shown in Fig. 9(a), six architectures are considered in the comparison: a single-element RX with an SNR of SNR_{Base} (taken as a baseline implementation), an N -element single-beam beamformer, an N -element analog beamformer with M sub-arrays, a fully connected N -element analog beamformer with M beams, a digital N -element beamformer with M beams, and an N -element time-modulated RX array with $(N + 1)$ beams. For the time-modulated RX array, two cases are considered: Case-1 where the bandwidth per beam is maintained as BW/N so that the overall occupied bandwidth of the time-modulated array is similar to that of other standard beamformers in the comparison, and Case-2 where the bandwidth per beam is maintained as $(M \times BW/N)$ so that the time-modulated RX array achieves the same overall throughput as other analog/digital multi-beam beamformers in the comparison. The following assumptions are made for all the architectures: (1) P_{RX} is the received power per element per beam, (2) the gain of each element is assumed to be unity, and (3) NF is the noise figure of each element up to the beamforming combiner. By analyzing the comparison data in Fig. 9(b), we can conclude that N -element/ M -beam analog fully connected and digital beamformers have high

(a)

	Single-Element RX	Single-Beam Beamformer	Analog Beamformer with M Sub-Arrays	Analog Fully Connected M -Beam Beamformer	Digital M -Beam Beamformer	This Work: Time-Modulated RX MIMO Array (Case-1)	This Work: Time-Modulated RX MIMO Array (Case-2)
Array Number of Elements	1	N	N	N	N	N	N
Number of Elements for Each Beam	1	N	N/M	N	N	N	N
Number of Elements for Each Beam over Time	1	N	N/M	N	N	1	1
Number of Concurrent Beams	1	1	M	M	M	$N + 1$	$N + 1$
Bandwidth per Beam	BW	BW	BW	BW	BW	$\sim BW/N$	$\sim M \times BW/N$
Occupied Bandwidth after Combiner	BW	BW	BW	BW	BW	$\sim BW$	$\sim M \times BW$
Overall Throughput (# Beams \times BW per Beam)	BW	BW	$M \times BW$	$M \times BW$	$M \times BW$	$\sim BW$	$\sim M \times BW$
Signal Power per Beam after Combiner (dBm)	P_{RX}	$P_{RX} + 20 \log N$	$P_{RX} + 20 \log(N/M)$	$P_{RX} - 10 \log M + 20 \log N$	$P_{RX} + 20 \log(N)$	$\sim P_{RX}$	$\sim P_{RX}$
Noise Power per Unit BW per Beam (dBm/Hz)	$-174 + NF$	$-174 + NF + 10 \log N$	$-174 + NF + 10 \log(N/M)$	$-174 + NF - 10 \log M + 10 \log N$	$-174 + NF + 10 \log(N)$	$-174 + NF$	$-174 + NF$
Integrated Noise Power per Beam (dBm)	$-174 + NF + 10 \log BW$	$-174 + NF + 10 \log BW + 10 \log N$	$-174 + NF + 10 \log BW + 10 \log(N/M)$	$-174 + NF - 10 \log M + 10 \log BW + 10 \log N$	$-174 + NF + 10 \log BW + 10 \log(N)$	$-174 + NF + 10 \log(BW/N)$	$-174 + NF + 10 \log(\frac{M}{N} BW)$
SNR per Beam after Combiner (dB)	$P_{RX} + 174 - NF - 10 \log BW = SNR_{Base}$	$SNR_{Base} + 10 \log N$	$SNR_{Base} + 10 \log(N/M)$	$SNR_{Base} + 10 \log N$	$SNR_{Base} + 10 \log N$	$SNR_{Base} + 10 \log N$	$SNR_{Base} + 10 \log(N/M)$
Implementation Complexity in a Relay	Simple	Moderate (N PSs)	Moderate (N PSs)	Complex ($M \times N$ PSs + $M \times N$ -Way Combiners)	Complex (N Down-Converters to Baseband + N ADCs + Digital Backend)	Simple (Switches + CLKs with Freq. \ll BW per Beam)	Simple (Switches + CLKs with Freq. \ll BW per Beam)

(b)

Fig. 9. A comparison between time-modulated RX arrays versus single-beam and multi-beam standard RX beamformers (a) architectures of the systems used in the comparison (b) performance comparison including the number of concurrent beams, the overall throughput, the SNR per beam, and the implementation complexity of each architecture if implemented in a relay.

complexity in scalable relay implementations operating on the fly, as the latter would require N down-converters to baseband, N high dynamic-range ADCs, and digital baseband, while the former would require $M \times N$ phase shifters (PSs) and M N -way power combiners. On the other hand, time-modulated RX arrays can achieve the multi-beam capability with low complexity in scalable relay implementations at either the cost of lower overall throughput (Case-1), or larger occupied bandwidth after the combiner and slightly lower SNR per beam (Case-2).

D. TX Effective-Isotropic-Radiated-Power

The effective-isotropic-radiated-power (EIRP) of the time-modulated TX relay array can be derived with the help of the time-modulation array factor expression derived in (7)-(8). As analyzed in detail in [31], time-modulated N -element TX arrays with $(N + 1)$ concurrent beams exhibit similar overall TX array efficiency as fully connected N -element/ M -beam analog/digital beamformers, where the TX array efficiency is defined as the total EIRP (by summing for all the beams)

Fig. 10. Analysis of the time-modulated relay operation considering the finite TX/RX antennas' isolation (a) existence of undesirable feedback paths from the TX antennas to the RX antennas (b) modeling of the relay operation considering the dominant leakage feedback path.

divided by the total power consumption of the array. That is, the time-modulation action upon the array splits the total EIRP of the array into $(N + 1)$ concurrent beams without degrading the array efficiency.

E. Antenna Isolation Impact Analysis

The finite isolation between the TX and RX antennas of the relay should be carefully analyzed to quantify its impact on the relay's operation. As shown in Fig. 10(a), due to the finite TX/RX antennas' isolation, there exists undesirable feedback paths from the relay's TX array to the relay's RX array. In general, for an N -element relay array having N TX elements and N RX elements, each of the TX antennas may generally have N undesirable leakage feedback paths to the N RX antennas, resulting in N^2 undesirable leakage paths on the array-level. However, considering the time-modulation operation of the proposed relay, only one TX and one RX elements are turned ON at any given time instant, resulting in only one dominant feedback path at any given time instant. For example, as shown in Fig. 10(a), from $t = 0$ to $t = T_{TM}/N$, only $Elem_{RX,1}$ and $Elem_{TX,1}$ are turned ON with the other RX and TX elements being OFF, resulting in only one considerable leakage path from $Elem_{TX,1}$ to $Elem_{RX,1}$ in this time duration. With this understanding, the relay's operation, considering the finite isolation, can be modeled at any time

Fig. 11. Impact of the finite TX/RX antennas' isolation on the relay's transfer function for different loop gain values and $\phi_2 = 0$ (a) normalized magnitude of the transfer function (b) phase of the transfer function.

instant as shown in Fig. 10(b). In this model, the desirable relay's feedforward path is modeled with a gain of G and a phase of ϕ_1 that respectively represent the gain and phase of each relay's element at the operation center frequency (ω_o). In addition, the undesirable feedback path at ω_o is modeled with a magnitude factor of H and a phase of ϕ_2 to represent the finite isolation between the RX and TX antennas of the same element ($Elem_{RX,m}$ and $Elem_{TX,m}$, where $m = 1, 2, \dots, N$). Utilizing this model, the transfer function of the relay at ω_o , which is equal to the transmitted signal (OUT) divided by the target received signal (IN), can be expressed at any time instant as:

$$TF = \frac{OUT}{IN} = \frac{Ge^{j\phi_1}}{1 + HG e^{j\phi_{tot}}} \quad (19)$$

where $\phi_{tot} = \phi_1 + \phi_2$. Consequently, the magnitude and phase of TF can be respectively derived as:

$$|TF| = \frac{G}{\sqrt{(1 + HG \cos \phi_{tot})^2 + H^2 G^2 \sin^2 \phi_{tot}}}, \quad (20)$$

$$\angle TF = \phi_1 - \tan^{-1} \frac{HG \sin \phi_{tot}}{1 + HG \cos \phi_{tot}}. \quad (21)$$

For the ideal scenario with infinite isolation ($H = 0$), $|TF|$ and $\angle TF$ are, as expected, equal to G and ϕ_1 respectively. However, due to the finite isolation in practical implementations, the feedback loop gain (LG), which is equal to HG , is non-zero and affects the relay's transfer function as given by (20) and (21). Fig. 11 shows the normalized magnitude and phase of the relay's transfer function plotted versus the relay's feedforward phase ϕ_1 for different loop gain values (while assuming that the feedback phase ϕ_2 is equal to 0). As can be seen from the results, for LG approximately

Fig. 12. Architecture scalability of the proposed time-modulated relay array.

≤ -10 dB, the impact of the feedback path on both the transfer function's magnitude and phase is minor. However, as LG increases above -10 dB, the relay's transfer function is considerably affected depending on the relay's feedforward phase (ϕ_1) value. Therefore, since the value of ϕ_1 may not be well controlled in practice, it is necessary to design the relay with loop gain below -10 dB to guarantee stable operation that is minorly affected by the antennas' finite isolation. More specifically, this corresponds to designing the relay's element forward gain (G) to be at least 10 dB lower than the isolation of the same-element TX/RX antennas. It is worth noting that a non-zero value of ϕ_2 will only horizontally shift the transfer function's magnitude and phase curves in Fig. 11, while having the same trend in the overall results. In addition, the presented analysis and simulation results of the finite antenna isolation are only valid under the assumption that the total loop delay (ϕ_{tot}/ω_o) is sufficiently smaller than the modulation symbol time of the target relay's received signal. This is to guarantee that the feedback leakage signal of a certain modulation symbol still affects the same symbol. In reality, the operation center frequency (ω_o) is usually much larger than the modulation bandwidth, and accordingly the former assumption is considered to be practical.

F. Architecture Scalability

Fig. 12 shows one possible approach to expand the proposed $1 \times N$ time-modulated relay array to a larger $M \times N$ relay array with enhanced array gain and without increasing the number of supported beams. In this approach, M tiled $1 \times N$ chips are arranged to construct a larger relay array size, where the corresponding elements of the M tiled chips (the elements of each column in the $M \times N$ relay array) operate in synchronization with the same time-modulation clock. Consequently, the $(N + 1)$ received/transmitted beams by each $1 \times N$ relay chip constructively add at the plane perpendicular to the array plane (plane x - z in Fig. 12), enhancing the array gain of each beam by a factor of $20 \log M$ without receiving/generating more beams. That is, in this approach, the N -dimension (x -direction) of the array controls the number of supported beams

Fig. 13. Non-line-of-sight link analysis for two users communicating through a reflective relay array.

and the M -dimension (y -direction) enhances the array gain by a factor of $20 \log M$. It is worth noting that the scalability approach of the proposed time-modulated relay in Fig. 12 does not require distributing any RF signals at the carrier frequency (120 GHz in this work) nor LO signals. It only includes distributing the time-modulation clock signals that only operate at the modulation rate (up to 1 GHz in this work), which exhibits much less power and complexity than generating and buffering high-speed LO signals.

G. NLOS Link Distance Analysis

In this subsection, the distance of a general NLOS wireless link through a reflective relay array is analyzed, and then the analysis is applied to the proposed time-modulated reflective relay array. As shown in Fig. 13, it is assumed that a TX labeled by user-1 is communicating with an RX labeled by user-2 through a NLOS wireless link enabled by a reflective relay array, where the distance from user-1 to the relay array is d_{TX} and the distance from the relay array to user-2 is d_{RX} . Further, it is assumed that the EIRP of user-1 is $EIRP_{TX}$ and the input power sensitivity of user-2 to achieve the target SNR of the entire link is $P_{RX,sens}$. Generally, the SNR at the back-end of user-2 will be affected through the NLOS link by the noise and distortion contributions of user-1, the noise and distortion contributions of the relay array, and the noise and distortion contributions of user-2. However, given the high mm-Wave operating frequency range of the proposed relay and the severe accompanying free-space path loss (FSPL), we assume here that the NLOS link is noise limited neglecting the distortion contributions for simplicity.

With the aid of the Friis transmission equation, the input power received by each element of the reflective relay array ($P_{RE,in}$) can be expressed as:

$$P_{RE,in} = EIRP_{TX} \cdot FSPL_{TX} \cdot G_{RE,Ant-RX} \quad (22)$$

where $FSPL_{TX}$ is equal to $\lambda_o^2 / (4\pi d_{TX})^2$ and $G_{RE,Ant-RX}$ is the relay's RX antenna gain. Assuming the relay's input

Fig. 14. On-chip antennas implementation (a) EM model of the 1×8 orthogonally-polarized RX and TX antenna arrays showing the utilized substrate grooving at the chip back side (b) simulated antenna array matching, TX-RX isolation, and radiation efficiency performance with and without substrate grooving (c) EM model of the folded-slot on-chip antenna element showing the antenna size (d) simulated antenna element radiation pattern at 120 GHz.

power sensitivity to satisfy the SNR requirement at the back-end of user-2 is $P_{RE,sens}$, the maximum distance of d_{TX} can be derived as:

$$d_{TX,max} = \frac{\lambda_o}{4\pi} \sqrt{\frac{EIRP_{TX} \cdot G_{RE,Ant-RX}}{P_{RE,sens}}}. \quad (23)$$

Now, assuming the gain of each element in the relay is $G_{RE,elem}$, the relay's TX antenna gain is $G_{RE,Ant-TX}$ and the relay's array factor is AF_{RE} , the EIRP of the relay ($EIRP_{RE}$) can be expressed in terms of relay's input received power ($P_{RE,in}$) as:

$$EIRP_{RE} = P_{RE,in} \cdot G_{RE,elem} \cdot G_{RE,Ant-TX} \cdot AF_{RE}. \quad (24)$$

Consequently, the power received by the RX of user-2 ($P_{RX,in}$) can be expressed as:

$$P_{RX,in} = EIRP_{RE} \cdot FSPL_{RX} \cdot G_{RX,Ant} \quad (25)$$

where $FSPL_{RX}$ is equal to $\lambda_o^2 / (4\pi d_{RX})^2$ and $G_{RX,Ant}$ is the RX antenna gain of user-2. Then, by setting $P_{RX,in}$ equal to the sensitivity of user-2 ($P_{RX,sens}$), the maximum distance of d_{RX} can be derived as:

$$d_{RX,max} = \frac{\lambda_o}{4\pi} \sqrt{\frac{EIRP_{RE} \cdot G_{RX,Ant}}{P_{RX,sens}}}. \quad (26)$$

By inspecting (23) and (26), it turns out that the maximum NLOS link distance ($d_{TX,max} + d_{RX,max}$) is a function of the design parameters of all the components in the NLOS path:

the reflective relay array, the external TX (user-1), and the external RX (user-2). For the relay part, the main contributing parameters, as revealed by (23)-(26), are the gain of the RX and TX antennas ($G_{RE,Ant-RX}$ and $G_{RE,Ant-TX}$), the gain of each element ($G_{RE,elem}$), and the array factor (AF_{RE}). For the proposed time-modulated relay array, the array factor for each of the $(N+1)$ beams of an $M \times N$ time-modulated relay array, as analyzed in Section IV.F, is equal to $20 \log M$, which is lower than a standard single-beam beamformer relay array by a factor of $20 \log N$, thus reducing $d_{RX,max}$. However, the proposed time-modulated relay array has the advantage of supporting $(N+1)$ simultaneous beams, offering a trade-off between the number of supported beams and the link distance for each beam.

H. End-Users IF Filter Considerations

As explained in Section III, due to the frequency-to-space mapping property of the time-modulated TX frontend of the relay, the relay broadcasts the beams to the final end-users at different frequency components ($f_{RF} \pm n f_{TM}$, where $n = 0, \pm 1, \dots, \pm N/2$) depending on their spatial angles. This imposes a requirement on the end-users' IF filter-banks to have a tunable IF center frequency capability to successfully pick the desired data stream/channel, from one to all the streams. In addition, to accommodate different values of modulation bandwidth in the system (and different scenarios of time-modulation frequencies), the end-users' IF filters are also required to provide a tunable bandwidth capability. Accordingly,

Fig. 15. Implementation of the 3-stage frontend amplifiers (a) circuit implementation along with its biasing conditions for LNA/PA (b) measured LNA small signal performance (c) measured PA large signal performance at 120 GHz.

Fig. 16. Simulated performance of the 3-stage amplifier with the tail time-modulation switch (a) impact of the tail switch upon gain and NF (b) transient test case under time-modulation operation with -20 dBm input power, and a 500-MHz (2-ns period) time-modulation clock with 12.5% duty-cycle.

for a practical deployment of the proposed system, end-users' IF filters with independent center frequency and bandwidth tuning capability are required like [53].

V. PROTOTYPE IMPLEMENTATION

Based on the proposed time-modulated LPTV relay architecture, a 120-GHz 8-element relay prototype is implemented in GF 22nm CMOS SOI process. The implementation comprises two orthogonally-polarized on-chip TX/RX antennas per

element, time-modulated 3-stage frontend amplifiers, an 8-way power combiner used in the RX array, and an 8-way power splitter used in the TX array.

A. On-Chip Antennas

The on-chip antennas are implemented based on a linearly-polarized compact folded-slot antenna structure at 120-GHz. The 3-D electromagnetic (EM) model of the 1×8 RX/TX antenna arrays is shown in Fig. 14(a). The RX antenna array is rotated 90° with respect to the TX antenna array, realizing orthogonal polarization to enhance TX/RX isolation. The antenna elements of the RX/TX arrays are placed on a 1.25 mm grid ($\lambda/2$ at 120 GHz) to eliminate grating lobes. They are designed for chip backside radiation, and substrate grooving, which is realized by post-processing the fabricated chips, is utilized to partially suppress the substrate modes and improve the radiation efficiency and isolation. As depicted in Fig. 14(b), simulations of the RX/TX antenna arrays show matching better than -10 dB across 113-138 GHz. In addition, with the adopted substrate grooving technique, the worst-case isolation between the TX and RX antennas is better than 33 dB across the whole D-band, and the radiation efficiency is 23.9% at 120 GHz with a lossy silicon substrate ($\rho = 7 \Omega\text{-cm}$). Compared to the standard scenario without substrate grooving, the substrate grooving technique, at 120 GHz, enhances the isolation by 3.4 dB and the radiation efficiency by 5.6%. The implementation of the linearly-polarized folded-slot unit antenna is shown in Fig. 14(c). It occupies an area of $450 \mu\text{m} \times 95 \mu\text{m}$. As shown in Fig. 14(d), the unit antenna, at 120 GHz, achieves a total gain of -2.8 dB at the back broadside, a 6 dB back-to-front ratio, and 1.5 dB beamwidth of $\pm 60^\circ$.

B. Frontend Amplifiers

The 3-stage frontend amplifiers are implemented using capacitively-neutralized common-source stages with compact

Fig. 17. Implementation of the 8-way power combiner/splitter (a) EM model of the utilized transmission-line based 2:1 Wilkinson unit cell (b) simulated S-parameters performance of the 2:1 Wilkinson unit cell (c) EM model of the 8-way Wilkinson power combiner/splitter (d) simulated S-parameters performance of the 8-way Wilkinson power combiner/splitter (e) simulated magnitude and phase performance of the 8-way Wilkinson power combiner/splitter.

transformer matching networks. The same amplifier is reused for the LNA and the PA with different biasing/supply voltages. The circuit implementation of the 3-stage amplifier, along with the biasing/supply voltages for both LNA/PA modes, is shown in Fig. 15(a). The time-modulation clock switches are implemented at the tail sources of the 3-stage amplifiers. This way, the switches, in the differential mode, appear at the ac-ground line of symmetry, minimizing their impact upon losses, noise figure (NF), linearity, and efficiency, compared to placing series switches in the signal path. The measured performance of the LNA mode of the amplifier is summarized in Fig. 15(b). The 3-stage LNA achieves a measured gain of 19 dB at 120 GHz, a 10-dB input matching bandwidth across 110-136 GHz, and the measured output matching is < -10 dB across the whole D-band. Figure 15(c) shows the measured large-signal performance of the PA mode of the amplifier. At 120 GHz, the 3-stage PA achieves a measured power gain of 17.6 dB, an output 1-dB compression point (OP_{1dB}) of 4.7 dBm, a saturated output power (P_{sat}) of 6.8 dBm, and a maximum power added efficiency (PAE_{max}) of 11.3%.

EM simulations of the time-modulation switches' impact upon the gain and the NF of the 3-stage amplifiers are shown in Fig. 16(a). The results show a degradation of only 0.12 dB and 0.08 dB in gain and NF respectively at 120 GHz. In addition, the simulated NF (while including the time-modulation

switches) is 5.8 dB at 120 GHz. A simulated transient test case of the 3-stage amplifier under time-modulation operation is also shown in Fig. 16(b). In this test case, the input to the 3-stage amplifier is a 120-GHz signal with -20 dBm power, and a 500-MHz (2-ns period) time-modulation clock with 12.5% duty-cycle is assumed. As shown in Fig. 16(b), the drivers' chain is able to efficiently drive the gate of the time-modulation switch with acceptable rise/fall times, and the output of the 3-stage amplifier tracks the time-modulation clock, implementing the target time-modulation operation.

C. Power Combiner/Splitter

The 8-way power combiner, used at the RX side, and the 8-way power splitter, used at the TX side, are implemented based on a wideband transmission-line based Wilkinson structure. The 3-D EM model of the transmission-line based 2:1 Wilkinson unit cell is shown in Fig. 17(a). It occupies an area of $300 \mu\text{m} \times 85 \mu\text{m}$. The simulation results, depicted in Fig. 17(b), show that the unit cell 2:1 Wilkinson achieves matching and isolation better than -15 dB across the whole D-band. Additionally, besides the 3 dB fundamental loss, it achieves an additional ohmic loss of 0.45 dB. Figure 17(c) shows the 3-D EM model of the 8-way Wilkinson power combiner/splitter. As shown in Fig. 17(d), it achieves matching and worst-case isolation between the 8 ports better than -15 dB across the

Fig. 18. Chip micrograph and packaging (a) chip front side (b) chip back side with the in-house substrate grooving (c) chip alignment with the PCB during the in-house flip-chip packaging.

whole D-band. Moreover, the simulated magnitude and phase imbalances between the 8 ports (Fig. 17(e)) is 0.2 dB and 1.2° respectively at 120 GHz. Additionally, besides the 9 dB fundamental loss, it achieves 3.5 dB additional losses that take into account both the ohmic losses of the Wilkinson cells and all the routing between them.

VI. MEASUREMENT RESULTS

The 8-element relay prototype is fabricated in GF 22nm CMOS FD-SOI process. Figure 18(a) shows the chip micrograph. The chip occupies an area of $10 \text{ mm} \times 2.5 \text{ mm}$. The chip is in-house post-processed to implement substrate grooves at the chip's back side as shown in Fig. 18(b). The chip is flip-chip packaged in house to an FR4 PCB and then mounted on a mechanical stand to constitute the device-under-test (DUT). The chip alignment with the PCB is shown in Fig. 18(c). OTA Continuous-Wave (CW) and modulation measurements through the DUT are conducted to demonstrate the NLOS multi-beam capabilities of the proposed relay.

A. CW Measurements

The CW measurement setup is shown in Fig. 19. Two external TXs (TX₁ and TX₂) and one external RX (RX₁), using three VDI D-band horn antennas, are used to emulate the transmitting/receiving wireless nodes communicating through the relay. TX₁ is built using the VDI D-band up-converter (CCU WR6.5), and TX₂ is built using the VDI D-band frequency extender (VNAX WR6.5). RX₁ is physically rotated by 90° to match the polarization of the relay TX antennas and suppress the LOS coupling with TX₁ and TX₂.

An absorber is further placed between the two external TXs and the external RX to further suppress the LOS path. Two synchronized arbitrary waveform generators (AWGs) are used to generate eight non-overlapping clocks that are used for the eight time-modulation clocks needed by the relay. The IF center frequency of RX₁ is adjusted at 6 GHz, so the received time-modulation sidebands are located at $6 \text{ GHz} \pm n f_{TM}$ at the IF side of RX₁. It is worth noting that for an 8-element time-modulated array, $n = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \pm 3$, and ± 4 correspond to spatial angles of $\theta = 0^\circ, \pm 14.48^\circ, \pm 30^\circ, \pm 48.59^\circ$, and $\pm 90^\circ$ respectively. Therefore, given that the implemented antennas can cover a scanning range of $\pm 60^\circ$, seven of these spatial angles ($\theta = 0^\circ, \pm 14.48^\circ, \pm 30^\circ$, and $\pm 48.59^\circ$) are of concern, and the two beams at $\pm 90^\circ$ lie outside the field-of-view range.

Four different 120-GHz NLOS CW measurement cases are presented in Fig. 20 with 1 TX enabled (cases A, B, and C) and 2 TXs enabled (case D), where $f_{TM} = 100 \text{ MHz}$ for the four cases. One external TX is only enabled (TX₂), for cases A, B, and C (which are shown in Fig. 20(a), (b), and (c) respectively), and sends a CW signal at 120 GHz from $\theta_{In2} = 0^\circ, -15^\circ$, and -30° (measured from the DUT broadside) respectively. For case D (shown in Fig. 20(d)), both TX₁ and TX₂ are enabled, and send two 120-GHz CW signals (S₁ and S₂ respectively) from $\theta_{In1} = 0^\circ$ and $\theta_{In2} = -30^\circ$ respectively with equal power levels. For the four cases, RX₁ is physically moved over $\pm 60^\circ$ scan range with a 5° step, while observing the IF spectrum of the RX₁ output at each angle. The radiation patterns, for the four cases, are then constructed as shown in Fig. 20, demonstrating the NLOS concurrent multi-beam reception and broadcasting capabilities of the proposed relay architecture. The array peak-to-null-ratio is measured to be around 20 dB with the main limiting factor being the inevitable mismatches between the 8-element circuits and on-chip antennas, which can be further improved by having on-chip amplitude/phase calibration units. It is worth noting that the peak gain roll-off of the radiation patterns in Fig. 20 as a function of the RX observation angle can be quantified by the derived magnitude of the time-modulation array factor in (7), which is given by the factor $\sin(\pi n/N)/(\pi n)$.

B. Modulation Measurements

The modulation measurement setup is shown in Fig. 21. The setup is similar to the CW setup except that a third AWG is used to generate the modulated data that goes through TX₁ and a Keysight UXN0704A oscilloscope is used to demodulate the IF output of RX₁. Two modulation test scenarios with 1 external TX enabled (scenario A) and 2 external TXs enabled (scenario B) are presented in Fig. 22(a), and (b) respectively. For scenario A, TX₂ is turned OFF and TX₁ at $\theta_{In1} = 0^\circ$ sends 16-QAM modulated data centered at 120 GHz. For scenario B, TX₂ (at $\theta_{In2} = -30^\circ$) is turned ON and sends a 120-GHz CW signal, and TX₁ has the same location and settings as scenario A. For both scenarios, RX₁ is moved to different angles ($15^\circ, 30^\circ$, and 50°) to demodulate the data stream sent by TX₁ by picking the proper IF frequency based on the angle, without the presence of the TX₂ stream

Fig. 19. NLOS CW measurement setup, where two external TXs and one external RX emulate the users communicating through the proposed relay.

Fig. 20. CW measurement results for four different test scenarios of a NLOS wireless link for 1 external TX enabled (cases A, B, and C) and 2 external TXs enabled (case D) (a) case A where TX₁ is OFF and TX₂ (at $\theta_{In2} = 0^\circ$) sends a CW signal at 120 GHz (b) case B where TX₁ is OFF and TX₂ (at $\theta_{In2} = -15^\circ$) sends a CW signal at 120 GHz (c) case C where TX₁ is OFF and TX₂ (at $\theta_{In2} = -30^\circ$) sends a CW signal at 120 GHz (d) case d where TX₁ (at $\theta_{In1} = 0^\circ$) and TX₂ (at $\theta_{In2} = -30^\circ$) send two independent CW streams at 120 GHz.

in scenario A and with the presence of the TX₂ stream in scenario B. For scenario A with one stream, the complete 120-GHz NLOS wireless link through the relay achieves a worst-case EVM_{RMS} of 6.4% and 8.9% for 16-QAM 1 and 2 Gbps respectively, while for scenario B with two concurrent streams, the achieved EVM_{RMS} is 9.5% and 12.2% for 16-QAM 1 and 2 Gbps respectively. EVM_{RMS} is degraded in scenario B compared to scenario A due to the impact of TX₂ upon TX₁ through the finite peak to null ratio. Limited by equipment, test scenarios with 2 different transmitted modulated streams

are not possible to conduct. However, the presented scenario B with 2 transmitted signals (1 modulated data stream + 1 CW) proves the multi-user multi-beam reception and broadcasting capabilities of the proposed relay while considering the impact of the finite peak-to-null-ratio.

Table I compares the proposed relay with the state-of-the-art CMOS active and passive reflective relays at mm-Wave and sub-THz frequencies. Compared to the relays reported in [21]–[23], [25], the proposed relay offers multi-beam capability. Compared to the multi-beam relay reported in [24], the pro-

Fig. 21. NLOS modulation measurement setup based on the proposed relay array.

Fig. 22. 16-QAM 250/500 MSym/s modulation measurement results for two different test scenarios of a NLOS wireless link for 1 external TX enabled (scenario A) and 2 external TXs enabled (scenario B) (a) scenario A where TX_1 (at $\theta_{In1} = 0^\circ$) sends 16-QAM modulated data at 120 GHz and TX_2 is OFF (b) scenario B where TX_1 (at $\theta_{In1} = 0^\circ$) sends 16-QAM modulated data at 120 GHz and TX_2 (at $\theta_{In2} = -30^\circ$) sends a 120-GHz CW signal with the same power level as the modulated data.

posed relay does not require LO/mixers per element, offering low-complexity and high-scalability relay architecture that suits D-MIMO applications. It is worth noting that the reported modulation round trip distance (0.2 m) for the proposed relay is still comparable to that of [24] (0.75 m) considering the larger free-space path loss at 120 GHz compared to 28 GHz ($4\times$ larger). In addition, the 2-Gbps data rate of the proposed work is the per-beam data rate, and when considering the fact that this beam is broadcast to six RX nodes (scenario A of Fig. 22(a)), the aggregate data rate of the entire network turns out to be 12 Gbps.

C. Link Distance

The 0.2-m round-trip distance of the proposed work is only measured for the scenario of a sub-array relay of 1×8 size,

and while using a simple off-the-shelf up-converter with an $EIRP_{P_{1dB}}$ of ~ 8 dBm to emulate the external TX user. As analyzed in Section IV.G, the distance of from the external TX to the relay (d_{TX}) can be improved by increasing the EIRP of the external TX, and the distance from the relay array to the external RX (d_{RX}) can be improved by increasing the gain of the relay element (while satisfying the isolation constraint as analyzed in Section IV.E) and scaling the relay array size. For example, in practice, by utilizing the 8×8 D-band TX phased-array in [16] for the external TX with a reported $EIRP_{P_{1dB}}$ of 31.5 dBm, d_{TX} can be enhanced by a factor of 15 (from 0.1 m to 1.5 m) for approximately the same demonstrated NLOS data rate and EVM. In addition, by enhancing the gain of the relay element by ~ 14 dB (from 7 dB to ~ 21 dB with the use of a D-band 2-stage driver at the combining node R) and

TABLE I
PERFORMANCE COMPARISON WITH THE STATE-OF-THE-ART CMOS ACTIVE AND PASSIVE REFLECTIVE RELAYS AT MM-WAVE AND SUB-THZ

	This Work	JSSC 2023 [24]	ISSCC 2025 [25]	TMTT 2021 [21]	ISSCC 2022 [22]	RFIC 2022 [23]
Center Frequency	120 GHz	28 GHz	120 GHz	25 GHz	260 GHz	60 GHz
Technology	22nm CMOS	65nm CMOS	22nm CMOS	65nm CMOS	22nm CMOS	65nm CMOS
Reflective Relay Type	Active	Active	Active	Active	Passive	Active
Beamforming Mechanism	Time-Modulation	True-Time-Delay and N-Path Filtering	5-bit Phase-Shifting	True-Time-Delay	1-bit Phase-Shifting	5-bit Phase-Shifting
Multi-Beam Capability?	Yes	Yes	No	No ⁽¹⁾	No	No
Need for LO/Mixers per Element?	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No
Demonstrated Array Size	1×8	1×4	4×4	1×4	98×98	2×2
Element Gain	7 dB ⁽²⁾	5.6 dB	23.6 dB	26 dB	-3 dB	15 dB
Element NF	5.8 dB (LNA) ⁽³⁾	4.5 dB (LNA) ⁽³⁾	7.3 dB (Chain)	3.8 dB (LNA) ⁽³⁾	NA	5.5 dB (Chain)
Element P _{sat}	6.8 dBm ⁽⁴⁾	3 dBm	6.8 dBm	11 dBm	NA	4.2 dBm
Element Power Consumption	32.2 mW ⁽⁵⁾	472 mW	100 mW	80 mW ⁽⁶⁾	0.1 mW ⁽⁷⁾	55 mW
Chip Area per Element	3.13 mm ²	3.85 mm ²	1.56 mm ²	7.9 mm ²	0.33 mm ²	1 mm ²
Demonstrated Data Rate	2 Gbps ⁽⁸⁾ 16-QAM Over 0.2 m ⁽⁹⁾	625 Mbps 32-QAM Over 0.75 m ⁽⁹⁾	6 Gbps 64-QAM Over 1.3 m ⁽⁹⁾	270 Mbps 64-QAM Over 5 m ⁽⁹⁾	No Modulation	400 Mbps QPSK ⁽¹⁰⁾

(1) Two concurrent transmitted beams are demonstrated, but not capable of transmitting concurrent modulated data streams

(2) Gain per beam including the on-chip TX and RX antennas, 3-stage LNA and PA, and Wilkinson fundamental and ohmic losses

(3) Simulated NF of LNA

(4) During continuously-ON operation

(5) 32.2 mW during TM operation (including TM 50-ohm terminations and drivers) and 128 mW during continuously-ON operation

(6) Only includes LO and baseband circuitry

(7) Integrated memory power consumption normalized per element with clock frequency = 100 kHz

(8) 2-Gbps data rate per beam, and considering that this beam is broadcast to six RX nodes, the aggregate data rate of the entire network is 12 Gbps

(9) Round-trip distance (distance from the external TX to the relay + distance from the relay to the external RX)

(10) The distance from the external TX to the relay is 1 m, but the distance from the relay to the external RX is not reported

by scaling the relay array size (with the scaling approach in Fig. 12) from 1×8 to 8×8, a total of ~32 dB can be added to the link budget from the relay to the external RX, enhancing d_{RX} by a factor of 40 (from 0.1 m to 4 m).

VII. CONCLUSION

A D-band scalable and LO-less multi-beam active relay array architecture with broadcasting capability is reported. The proposed relay architecture targets 6G D-MIMO networks for fronthaul mobile communication and advanced factory automation, where the multi-beam reception and broadcasting capabilities of the proposed relay can directly enhance the latency, reliability, and throughput of these networks. It utilizes time-modulation at both of its receiving and transmitting frontends, and the resulting LPTV nature enables the concurrent reception and transmission of the multi-beams with multiple independent data streams. Other than the D-band, the relay architecture is frequency agnostic and can be well scaled to other higher/lower mm-Wave and sub-THz frequencies. Its LO-less nature ensures a scalable and low-complexity relay implementation. In addition, the processing of the beams in the RF domain enables low-latency communication. To

demonstrate the capabilities of the proposed relay architecture, a 120-GHz 8-element relay array prototype with on-chip orthogonally-polarized RX/TX antenna arrays is implemented in GF 22nm FD-SOI. OTA modulation measurements demonstrate successful D-band 16-QAM NLOS wireless links achieving 2 Gbps per beam with worst-case EVM_{RMS} of 8.9% in the case of one external TX node communicating through the relay with up to six RX nodes and worst-case EVM_{RMS} of 12.2% in the case of two external TX nodes communicating through the relay with up to five RX nodes.

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